

wet. It has medium bold grains (1,000-grain weight = 24.0 g) and white kernels. Height is 110 cm, with leaf area index about 3.5, harvest index 0.46, and solar energy utilization 1.11% in the wet and 0.94% in the dry seasons.

Swarnaprabha had the highest dry matter and grain yield in one wet and two dry seasons. Crop growth rate during reproductive and ripening stages, sink capacity, and postflowering dry matter accumulation were high, resulting in high spikelet

and grain numbers/m². Yields were over 4.5 and 5.5 t/ha in the wet and dry seasons.

Yield difference between seasons was marginal, showing its stability. □

Two upland rice varieties recommended for release in Nigeria

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To identify high-yielding and short-duration varieties for upland environments, five entries selected from local testing at Ibadan were evaluated in multilocational trials during the 1984 and 1985 wet seasons. IRAT133 and IRAT144 were the best performers (see table). They also had

Performance of IRAT133 and IRAT144 in upland environments in Nigeria.

Variety	Height (cm)	Days to flowering	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase (%) over check
IRAT144	127	75	3.0	43
IRAT133	116	72	2.9	38
ITA257 (check)	118	72	2.1	—

^aAv of 1984 and 1985 multilocational trials.

the highest yields in 1983 Ibadan trials. The Third National Conference of the Nationally Coordinated Research Project on Rice (Apr 1986) has recommended that they be released for cultivation.

IRAT133 and IRAT144 are crosses

of IRAT13 and IRAT10, introduced from Ivory Coast. They have short duration and disease and drought resistance. IRAT133 is short, IRAT144 is medium and has the better plant type. □

Two high-yielding varieties for southern Andhra Pradesh wet season

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NLR27999 and NLR9672-96 are semidwarf varieties with higher yield potentials than NLR9672 and NLR9674. Both have grain dormancy after harvest and yield as high as 6.5 t/ha in the wet season. Both yield well, even with 60-d-old seedlings. NLR27999 is suitable for late planting, up to the end of Oct.

NLR9672-96 is a secondary selection from NLR9672, derived from Bulk H-9/ Millek kuening. NLR27999 is a cross derivative of RP3 1-49-2/ BCPl. Bulk H-9 and BCPl are tall, Molagolukulu-grain type. Millek kuening and RP31-49-2 are resistant to blast (Bl).

Grains of NLR27999 and NLR9672-96 are short and bold with dirty brown

Table 1. Agronomic traits of NLR27999 and NLR9672-96 and pest and disease reactions. Andhra Pradesh, India.

Character	NLR27999	NLR9672-96	NLR9672	NLR9674
Duration (d)	160-170	150-160	150-160	160-170
Plant type	Semidwarf, compact tillering, nonlodging, light green foliage with erect flag leaf	Semidwarf, compact tillering, nonlodging, light green foliage with droopy flag leaf	Semidwarf, compact tillering, nonlodging, light green foliage with droopy flag leaf	Semidwarf, compact tillering, nonlodging, light green foliage with erect flag leaf
Plant height (cm)	113	119	100	104
Tillering ability	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Panicles/m ²	289	282	248	269
Grains/panicle	291	301	339	326
1000-grain weight (g)	21.8	21.5	23.5	22.5
Dormancy	Present	Present	Present	Present
Reaction to Blast	Moderately resistant	Moderately resistant	Susceptible	Susceptible
Bacterial blight	Moderately resistant	Moderately resistant	Moderately resistant	Susceptible
Brown plant-hopper	Resistant	Resistant	Resistant	Resistant
Gall midge	Susceptible	Susceptible	Susceptible	Susceptible

glumes, similar to that of traditional Molagolukulu. Grain shedding at maturity is less than in NLR9672. Threshability is good. Milled rice is

white and translucent.

NLR9672-96 matures in 150-160 d and NLR27999 in 160-170 d. Both are weakly photoperiod sensitive and are